

SYNONYMY OF MILITARY-TECHNICAL TERMS IN THE GERMAN AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the synonymous relationships that have historically developed in terminology related to military equipment in the German and Uzbek languages. It should be noted that in this case, *synonymy* is studied on the basis of the causal intentional development of semantic, grammatical and word-formation systems of genetically heterogeneous languages. The study also examines the derivation of absolute and semantic substantive, verbal adjectival, hybrid and borrowed synonyms from Latin and Greek, and analyzes the identical and distinctive aspects of the synonymy of the two languages. A comparative description of the original, derivative and synonymous terminology of a number of areas of military-technical vocabulary of the German and Uzbek languages was carried out.

Keywords: Synonymy, Term, Terminology, German language, Uzbek language, Military Terms, Technical Terms, Origin, Lexicology.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the linguistic system, forms of lexical-semantic relations such as homonymy, synonymy and hyponymy serve to enrich the vocabulary and provide functional diversity of speech. As is known, the language system, in particular the terminological system, is built on paradigmatic (associative), syntagmatic and derivational types of relations between linguistic units. This linguistic aspect is

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still understudied in research terms. According to L. A. Novikov, the structure of paradigmatic relations is made up of “... *first of all, synonymous, antonymic, polysemic, taxonomic connections*” (Новиков 1991). L. A. Novikov clearly formulated four paradigmatic relations, which are widely studied in the terminological system.

About the causality and systematic nature of paradigmatic connections, L. A. Nefedova writes the following: “*Paradigmatic relationships are relationships that connect elements of language on the basis of commonality in form, meaning, or both at the same time. Paradigmatic relations as relations at the interlexical level postulate the separateness of a word in a number of verbal units comparable to it according to the principles of the concept reflected in the lexical meaning of the word, and according to differences in the form of words*” (Нефедова 2013: 150). Of course, in synonymy the lexical meaning of a word is of great importance.

According to I. Barz “*synonymy is especially characteristic of the early stages of the formation of a terminological system, when the natural (or artificial) selection of the best term has not yet occurred and many proposed variants of the terminological name coexist*” (Barz 1997: 265). I. Barz also notes that “*the use of synonyms often causes uncertainty in the designation of the same concept by different words and leads to difficulties in mutual understanding*” (Barz 1997: 266). After conducting a series of studies, D.S. Lotte argued that “*in terminology, polysemy and synonymy are harmful, therefore, as far as possible, they should be avoided*” (Лотте 1961: 21). Based on the above, the presence of synonymy in terminology is not an acceptable phenomenon, and this pattern in the Uzbek language has also turned into an almost strict rule.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

One of the pressing issues of terminology is the functioning of synonyms in modern industry terminology systems. The problem of synonymy of terms has been repeatedly raised and discussed by linguists and terminologists, such as D.S. Lotte (1961), A. V. Lagutina (1967), V. P. Danilenko (1971), S. V. Grinev (1993), V. A. Tatarinov (2006) and many others.

Despite the fairly deep development of this problem, questions remain open about the definition of the concept of “*synonymous terms*”, about the paradigm of “*synonymy*” and “*variability*”, as well as about the classification of synonymous terms.

German linguist Thea Schippan defines synonyms as names of the same denotation, having the same core meaning and differing in peripheral denotative semes or connotative features, or both: *“Als Synonyme betrachten wir somit Lexeme, die Benennungen des gleichen Denotats sind, und deshalb über einen Kern gleicher Bedeutungselemente verfügen, sich aber durch periphere denotative Seme oder konnotative Merkmale oder durch beides unterscheiden können”* (Schippan 1992: 207).

The definition of synonyms proposed by M. Schwarz seems interesting: *“... synonyms can be defined as words belonging to the same part of speech, the meanings of which contain identical elements; the differing elements are steadily neutralized in certain portions. In other words, words can be recognized as synonyms if they are opposed only by such semantic features that in certain contexts become insignificant”* (Schwarz 1993: 175).

According to the above definitions, in common vocabulary, synonyms are understood as identical in meaning or different, but close in meaning, lexical units. Stylistic synonyms are characteristic of a general literary language. They name the same thing, *“but relate it to different concepts and thereby, through naming, reveal different properties of this thing”* (Schwarz 1993: 177). Synonymy in common literary language is one of the most expressive stylistic means and is considered as a positive phenomenon.

In the linguistic literature there is no consensus on terminological synonymy. Many scientists recognize the existence of synonymous terms, although they consider terminological synonymy an undesirable phenomenon and have a negative attitude towards the artificial creation of synonymous terms.

There is also the opposite opinion. Thus, a researcher of synonyms in English and American literature on railway transport, Z. M. Bulat, evaluates synonymy in the industry terminology system as a positive phenomenon: *“Synonyms are rightly considered an indicator of the richness, development, and flexibility of the language. Differing in shades of meaning, terms-phrases-synonyms perform a number of functions: they contribute to the accuracy and clarity of statements, phonetically diversify speech, and determine a variety of styles of oral and written speech”* (Булат 1970: 14).

The famous Russian linguist-terminologist V. A. Tatarinov also has a positive attitude towards terminological synonymy. He believes that a synonym in terminology is an active linguistic means of fixing a new view on the subject of thought, that with the help of the plurality of nominative means of language, the lability of mental structures is realized, thus, *“the higher the level of development of science, the more synonymous the thinking of a specialist”* (Татаринов 2006: 175). Synonymy of terms is defined as *“a type of semantic relations of terms, consisting in the ability of terminological units to denote the same special concept to indicate its various essential or non-essential features, as well as to express the stylistic attitude of the author to the material being presented”* (Татаринов 2006: 172). Considering terminological synonymy, V. A. Tatarinov notes that *“in relation to terms, it is necessary to keep in mind that synonyms of a term always name one concept, but have partial differences in identifying individual aspects of the concept (subject, phenomenon), which is necessary in scientific process”* (Татаринов 2006: 190]. V. A. Tatarinov also believes that *“the definition of synonyms at the metalinguistic level as units that are correlated in semantic terms, but differ in peripheral semantics, perfectly reflects the essence of terminological synonymy”* (Татаринов 2006: 173).

V. P. Danilenko considers synonymous terms in a similar way: *“In terminology, synonyms correspond to the same concept and object, they do not characterize its different properties”* (Даниленко 1971: 73).

S. V. Grinev proposes a generalizing term *“equivalence”*, the meaning of which *“would include not only the relations of absolute and conditional synonymy of terms (for which the term “synonymy” is suitable), but also the equivalence of multilingual terms”* (Гринев 1993: 109). At the same time, he distinguishes between equivalent terms of one language and equivalent terms in different languages. S.V. Grinev refers to equivalent terms of one language as synonymous terms (synonymous terms) of one language with identical or similar meaning, and to multilingual equivalent terms - equivalents (multilingual terms with identical or similar meaning (Гринев 1993: 109).

Recognizing the presence of synonymy in terminology, a number of terminologists distinguish between the following terms *“synonym”*, *“variant”* and *“doublet”*. V. M. Leichik believes that *“variation of a term is a specific implementation of the general theory of variation, which manifests itself both in the language as a whole and in its individual varieties. At the same time, there is substantive, formal, functional and stylistic variation in terminology”* (Лейчик 2009:

73-74). By studying functional variation in terminology, E. V. Medvedeva also believes that the fundamental and general property of language is variation, and synonymy is one of the possible forms of its implementation (Медведева 2009: 318).

Considering the paradigm of the terms “*synonymy*” and “*variation*,” S. V. Grinev writes that “*with a strict approach to variation (which, in particular, is required by automation of terminological activity), lexemes that differ even by one letter are different independent terms, and since they serve to name one concept, they fully correspond to the characteristics of absolute synonyms*” (Гринев 1993: 109-110).

As K. Ya. Averbukh notes, “*only absolute synonyms (doublets), as well as synonyms and homonyms by significatum, can be considered as variants of a term*” (Авербух 2006: 15).

The opposite opinion is defended by V. A. Tatarinov, who believes that “*a synonym in terminology is far from a doublet, but an active linguistic means of fixing a new view on the subject of thought and when identifying synonyms, one should proceed from the following trichotomy: formal-structural variants, onomasiological variants and synonyms*” (Татаринов 2006: 173).

According to V.P. Danilenko, synonyms in terminology have other functions and, as a rule, do not perform stylistic functions (Даниленко 1971: 74).

There is an opinion that the presence of synonymous terms causes specialists to strive to find the difference between them, which leads to an incorrect understanding of the content. As an analysis of the literature on terminological synonymy shows, there are different points of view on this issue. But at the same time, the opinions of scientists agree that synonymy is an inevitable product of the development of terminology. This is also noted by H. Nematov, N. Vohidova and I. Yunusova, “*the terminology of any field of knowledge serves the communication of specialists in this field in a variety of areas of their activity: speaking at symposia and conferences, teaching at a university, writing articles, etc. Thus, different qualities are required from terms, depending on the specific goals of communication. Therefore, there is a need to designate the same concept using several terms. Also, synonymous terms help avoid dullness and monotony of scientific presentation. And this means that the complete elimination of synonymy when streamlining terminology will functionally weaken it, and will not make it more perfect*” (Nematov, Vohidova & Yunusova 2006: 122).

III. ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In the context of using synonymy in a scientific style, its semantic code does not allow variations, while in other styles this prohibition is not relevant. This general theoretical position can be transformed into the sphere of military-technical terms of the German and Uzbek languages, which are the object of our comparative study.

To date, the study of military-technical terms in these languages is at different stages of its development. If German military-technical terminology is distinguished by its theoretical development, then Uzbek military-technical terminology has not yet been the object of special scientific research. Based on this, the issue of creating a theoretical basis and researching Uzbek military-technical terminology in a comparative aspect is urgent, since in the formation of Uzbek military-technical terminology there is a direct influence of the Russian language, and an indirect influence of the German language. Military-technical terms in both the Uzbek and German languages represent a specific group of vocabulary, inherent only in this area and forming a single paradigmatic system.

When conducting a comparative study of the lexical composition of military-technical terminology of the two indicated languages, cases of polysemy and synonymy were noted. These linguistic phenomena are found when denoting the components of equipment and weapons, as well as actions and static states associated with them.

Thus, for example, in the Uzbek professional military vocabulary there is the term “*tank*”; in the German language there are a set of concepts that form a synonymous word-line “*Panzer*”, “*Tank*”, “*Schale*”, “*Harnisch*” etc. A lot of similar examples can be found. However, synonyms in the lexical layer of a language, devoid of any differences, in most cases are eliminated in the process of language development, which experiences semantic and stylistic changes (Sharafutdinowa 2001: 115). A narrowing of the scope of use of one of the synonymous words may occur as a result of the rare use of this word in the language. Recognition of synonymy in terminological systems indicates that the nature of synonymous relations in language and terminology is different.

M. M. Mirtozhiev notes that synonyms are divided into two types, which differ in the semantic relationship in which the words are located: 1) synonyms, where the semantic relationships of words are based on sameness, are absolute synonyms; 2) synonyms, where the

semantic relationships of words are based on complete identity, are semantic synonyms (Миртожиев 2010: 190-198].

In the works of A. Madvaliev they are called doublet synonyms (Мадвалиев 2017: 88). A large number of military-technical terms in the Uzbek language are international and borrowed. According to A. Madvaliev, *“international terms that came into the Uzbek language are divided into two groups: a) international terms that came ready-made from Western European languages into the Russian language and through it into the Uzbek language; b) terms created on the basis of international terms, but on the basis of the Russian language. When creating terms of this last type or in the process of adopting some internationalisms in semi-calculation, prepositive international term elements were combined with Russian words and formed a group of words of a separate type - hybrid words”* (Мадвалиев 2017: 49). Supporting this opinion, we will call such words *“hybrid words consisting of multilingual elements.”*

Lexico-semantic relations, for example, in the synonymy of terms are formed from components that include the same term. Among military-technical terms, absolute terms are especially common. The results of the analysis show that absolute synonyms with the same semantic relationships are represented by one word in the Uzbek language and two or more words in the German language.

M.K. Khakimova expresses the opinion that in synonymous series consisting of abstract adjectives, the differentiation of meanings differs in the volume of the given concept, as well as the degree of familiarity of the words and the scope of their application (Хакимова 2019: 26). This opinion is in a certain sense very correct, since it accurately shows the use of adjectives in relation to people and inanimate objects, the scope of application of the word. Such words have the same meaning in German and Uzbek languages, but have a number of synonyms in German. However, this indicates that these words have the same meaning and they have a common scope of application.

According to M. M. Mirtozhiev, lexical meanings are never absolutely equal (Миртожиев 2010: 198). In semantic synonyms, all semes of the lexical meanings of words: archiseme, integral seme, differential seme must be the same.

R. Sharopova, studying the synonymy of socio-political terminology, identified two groups of synonyms: 1. Synonymy of original or derived terms. 2. Synonymy of compound terms

(Шаропова 2019: 16). Using this model, we also identified a similar series of synonyms in the German and Uzbek languages.

For example: 1) “*dreistrahliges Flugzeug*” // “*Flugzeug mit drei Strahtriebwerken*” // “*Strahlflugzeug mit drei Triebwerken*” – “*uch dvigatelli reaktiv samolyot*”; 2) “*Kippflügelflugzeug*” // “*Kippflügler*” – “*egilgan qanotli samolyot*” (Шарафутдинова 2008: 214).

Consequently, lexical differences in compound terms are not observed in the German and Uzbek languages, but on the contrary, the presence of similar aspects has been revealed. The combination of adjectives with nouns indicates that there are many similarities in two foreign languages.

In military-technical terminology, one of the synonyms is usually a foreign language borrowing. Many foreign words and terms were borrowed, adapted, translated, and translated into the Uzbek language, thus becoming semantic synonyms. The specialist understands and applies such words without difficulty. This type of synonymy is often found among military-technical terms. So, for example, the term “*die Adaptation*” – “*adaptatsiya*” — is a lexeme of Latin origin “*adaptation*”, a German loanword that was also borrowed into Uzbek via Russian.

International terminology refers mainly to Greek and Latin, which are considered classical languages. It is known that Greek and Latin are part of the ancient Indo-European languages. Their influence on related languages, that is, on the languages of this family, is great. Consequently, the main source of international vocabulary that has emerged in modern languages is Greek and Latin. The same applies to the terminological systems of the German and Uzbek languages.

According to the degree of similarity of meanings, synonymous terms are divided into absolute synonyms (German “*totale Synonyme*”) (synonyms with the same meaning) and conditional synonyms (German “*partielle Synonyme*”) (relative, partial; synonyms with a similar meaning). Absolute synonyms are divided into variants (synonyms obtained by varying the form of the term) and doublets (absolute synonyms with different forms).

Studying the relationship between the terms “*absolute synonym*” and “*doublet*” we draw the following conclusion: the term “*terminological synonymy*” most adequately expresses the presence of several names for one signified. An example of an absolute synonym would be the term “*Zugschraubenflugzeug*” // “*Flugzeug mit Zugschrauben*” – “*tortuvchi vintli samolyot*” (Шарафутдинова 2008: 215). Along with absolute synonyms, partial (conditional) synonymous

terms are used, which are synonyms only in a certain context or genre of text. For example: “*Tragflügel*” – “*qanot*”. By structure, i.e. depending on the morphemic composition, synonyms can have different roots: “*Hafen*” // “*Flugplatz*” // “*Landefläche*” – “*aerodrom*” (Шарафутдинова 2008: 216).

In the German military aviation terminology system, there are much more synonymous terms with the same root than synonyms with different roots. This is also facilitated by the functioning of a large number of verbal nouns formed by different derivational suffixes. For example: “*Abfangen*” // “*Abfangung*” – “*raqib samolyotlarini tutish*”; “*Durchflug*” // “*Durchfliegen*” – “*parvoz*” (Шарафутдинова 2008: 217).

IV. CONCLUSION

Thus, synonymy is widespread in the military-technical terminology of both the Uzbek and German languages, and the reasons for the origin of synonyms are related to the methods of forming the terminological system. This is characteristic of all forms of manifestation of synonymy, especially the initial stages of the formation of a terminological system. The military-technical terms that exist to this day have appeared and are appearing on the basis of many variants with natural and artificial selection of terms.

The results of the analysis showed that synonymy is widely used in military-technical terminology and that absolute synonyms with the same semantic relationships are usually represented by one word in the Uzbek language and two or more words in the German language. On the other hand, semantic synonyms are less productive in the military-technical vocabulary of both languages. In addition, synonymous relations of compound terms in the German language are more productive than in the Uzbek language. A significant part of foreign military-technical vocabulary was assimilated from Russian into Uzbek without calquing. It was also concluded that military-technical terminology was formed by the consistent use of Latin-Greek terms borrowed from both Uzbek and German.

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